

RESEARCH ARTICLE**Effect of Corporate Social Responsibilities on Turnover of Brewery Firms in Nigeria****Edeh, Ijeoma Thelma¹, Inyiama, Oliver Ikechukwu², Akparhuere, Godwin Oghenekohwo³**^{1,2&3}Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu, Nigeria***Corresponding Author: Edeh, Ijeoma Thelma | Department of Accountancy, Enugu State University of Science and Technology Enugu State, Enugu****ABSTRACT**

The study is an ex-post facto research which examines effect of Corporate Social Responsibilities on turnover of Breweries firms in Nigeria using secondary data from three selected Breweries firms in Nigeria. The secondary data used were generated from annual report of Nigeria Breweries Plc, Guinness Nigeria Plc and International Breweries Plc, Turnover is the independent variable of the study and the dependent variable is Corporate Social Responsibility of Nigeria's Breweries firm for the year under study. Regression Analysis was used for the data analysis. Findings indicate that under the simple regression analysis was that p-value = 0.000, hence we concluded that the study was able to reveal that donations and gifts component of corporate social responsibility is significant and needs to be continuously pursued to make the environment stable for both the communities and the companies involved. However, public health and education and training were not significant. So the average judgement of this outcome is that corporate social responsibility has not really made much impact in the area of brewery firms in Nigeria. The study recommends that Breweries in Nigeria should buckle up in public and safety efforts in the areas where they operate; and the Management of breweries in Nigeria should as a matter of responsibility continue to give donations and gifts to charities and orphanages, sports entertainments, infrastructural development and such like. This will reduce industrial unrests, agitations and protests in the areas where the firms are located.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibilities; Turnover of Brewery Firms; Nigeria

Introduction

Brewery firms are essentially firms that manufacture beer and similar alcoholic drinks and consumable foods and beverages for the Nigerian public. Against the backdrop of Nigeria's fragile macroeconomic environment, the brewery sector performance has remained pressured despite a robust population advantage estimated at over 200 million people. Analysis of the sector reveals that industry revenue grew by a CAGR of 5.1% between 2017 and 2019 to N594.3bn from N511.8bn. Notwithstanding, the sector is not out of the woods yet as intense competition still presents limited scope for volume growth while the impact of regulation and higher cost pressures continue to weigh heavily on the overall performance.

Equally, macroeconomic fundamentals are little changed in favour of consumer spending in the face of persistent weak economic growth, currency pressures, and higher unemployment & inflation rates. Notably, data from the NBS shows that consumers spent the least on alcoholic drinks at N150.2bn, representing 0.4% of total consumption expenditure in the last decade. This is not unexpected given the

poor state of consumer's disposable income with a slow CAGR of 1.7% in the last five years as well as the discretionary nature of alcohol consumption (Proshare.com).

While Nigeria's large population and strong demographic appeal are some of the key industry growth propellers, it has been noted that the sector is still faced with tough fiscal regulations including the June 2018 new excise duty burden on beer, wines and spirits as well as the new VAT rate of 7.5% implemented in February 2020. Likewise, external risk factors mainly lower oil prices are also constraints to FX capital flows for the importation of essential raw and packaging materials such as barley and aluminium cans. Meanwhile the insecurity issues in the Middle-belt region still persists, upsetting the supply of locally sourced raw materials such as rice and sorghum, thus threatening brewer's backward integration strategies with added cost pressures. Given these changing dynamics and the limited room for pricing, brewers have been compelled to actively seek to improve efficiency across the value chain through

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backward integration as well as to retain and increase market share through brand visibility. Observably, as the battle for market share deepens, industry players continue to leverage product innovations to remain competitive in the face of constrained pricing actions.

As at full year 2019, the market structure of the Nigerian brewery industry is still oligopolistic with four (4) major listed players - Nigerian Breweries Plc (NB), International Breweries Plc (INTBREW), Guinness Nigeria Plc (GUINNESS) and Champion Breweries Plc (CHAMPION).

Overall, it has been noted that growing volumes and improving profitability remains a tight rope to walk especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. It is believed short term growth triggers are limited considering the devastating impact of the pandemic on consumer's income. Therefore, we suspect the trend of increased product offerings especially at the mainstream and value segments of the market as well as targeted marketing and advertising strategies would be sustained over the short to medium term. In addition, despite the recent drive to boost local supply of raw materials, brewers remain largely dependent on importation, still accounting for over 40.0% of raw material components on the average.

Meanwhile, increased competition has strongly restricted the scope for pricing actions to support margins due to cost pressures, fragile consumer spending and shifting consumer preferences. Therefore, analysts now expect the response to FX devaluation and COVID-19 economic shocks to largely influence pricing decisions in the industry as consumers' disposable income takes a hit.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a self-regulating business model that helps a company be socially accountable—to itself, its stakeholders, and the public. By practicing corporate social responsibility, also called corporate citizenship, companies can be conscious of the kind of impact they are having on all aspects of society, including economic, social, and environmental.

To engage in CSR means that, in the ordinary course of business, a company is operating in ways that enhances society and the environment, instead of contributing negatively to them. Corporate social responsibility is a broad concept that can take many forms depending on the company and industry. Through CSR programs, philanthropy, and volunteer efforts, businesses can benefit society while boosting their brands (Fernando, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The subject of corporate social responsibility is one of the contemporary studies that continue to reoccur in research. Empirical information shows that there were studies mainly in the oil and gas industries, the manufacturing companies of various goods and in related industries where production is hazardous. Though many studies have been done, the area of CRS in brewery firms is not very much addressed as regards its effect on the turnover of the firms. This study is focused on the effect of corporate social responsibility on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study is to determine the effect of corporate social responsibility on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria. The following specific objectives have been formulated to in order to realize the main objective, namely:

- i) To ascertain the effect of health and safety on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.
- ii) To evaluate and the effect of education training on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria
- iii) To verify the effect of donations on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria

Research Questions

- i) To what extent does health and safety affect turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria?
- ii) How does education and training affect turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria?
- iii) What effect do donations have on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria?

Statement of Hypotheses

- H₁: Health and safety do not have significant effect on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.
- H₂: Education does not have significant effect on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.
- H₃: Donations do not have significant effect on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This study will be of great significance to certain interest groups, namely:

The management of brewery firms in Nigeria

Management of brewery firms and similar industries will find it very useful for planning and decision making, forecasting and estimation of business trends in the brewery sector in Nigeria. The empirical evidence from this report is capable of increasing the confidence and integrity of previous information on the subject matter.

Research students in related fields

The empirical materials employed in this report will be useful for further studies in related fields thereby enriching the bodies of the works. The efforts of students carrying out related researches will be easier and timely.

Analysts

The findings will serve the purpose of analysis of researches in the future by interested analysts. It is expected that references will continue to be added to this work in similar topics during discussions by potential analysts.

Members of the General Public

The issues of corporate social responsibility continue to dominate these contemporary studies and members of the general public are very sensitive to this field. Therefore, this study is very significant as it would help to educate members of the public concerning the concept of corporate social responsibility with particular interest in the Nigeria breweries.

Scope of the study

This research work was centered on the effect of corporate social responsibilities on turnover of Breweries firms in Nigeria

Operational Definition of Terms

For the purpose of clear understanding, the researcher has defined the following terms as follows:

i) Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is a self-regulating business ideal that helps a company be socially accountable—to itself, its stakeholders, and the public.

ii) Breweries

A company that makes beer is called either a brewery or a brewing company.

iii) Turnover

Turnover is an accounting concept that calculates how quickly a business conducts its operations.

Conceptual Review

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

Companies are facing increasing demands that, they look beyond their own interests and prioritize those of the societies in which they operate (Broomhill, 2007). The view that, business enterprises have responsibilities to society beyond that of making profits for shareholders has been around for centuries (Carroll and Shabana, 2010). Corporate Social Responsibility can be defined as what an organisation does that affects the society in which it exist (Stoner, Freeman & Gilbert, 2006). Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as a process of achieving business success in such a way to honor ethical values, respect people, communities, and the natural environment. More so, he also opined that CSR means to address the legal, ethical, commercial and the society expectations from business entity and arrived at the reasonable decisions that balance the claims of all key stakeholders (Osei-Tete, 2010).

Ademosu (2008) refers to Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as constituting what an organization does to contribute to the social, economic, political or educational development of the community where it is located, but which it is not compelled to do by any law. Aaronson (2003) states that CSR is a business decision making linked to ethical values in compliance with legal requirements, and respect for people, communities, and the environment around the world.

Baker (2006:2) argues that corporate social responsibility is about how companies manage the business processes to produce and overall positive impact on society. It refers to sets of actions that appear to further some social good, beyond the interests of the firm and that which is required by law (McWilliams & Siegel, 2000). Important in this definition is that CSR activities are on a voluntary basis, going beyond the firm's legal and contractual obligations. As such it involves a wide range of activities such as being employee-friendly, environment-friendly, and respectful of communities where the firms' plants are located, and even investor-friendly (Bénabou and Tirole, 2010).

Enahoro, Akinyomi and Olutoye (2013) posit that corporate social responsibility (CSR) covers a wide range of issues such as plant closures, employee relations, human rights, corporate ethics, community relations and the environment. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) explains as corporate actions that protect and improve the firm's resources for typical purposes such as abolishing poverty, helping to solve urban problems, protecting consumers, supporting education, being actively involved in environmental issues, providing good products and enhancing the quality of life generally. In a broader sense, it includes a commitment to achieve a balance between the interest and need of each stakeholder, including the organization, employees, the environment and the society where it operates (Abiahu, Udeh, and Ogbekhilu, 2018).

Reasons for Corporate Social Responsibility

Scholars have given various reasons for organisation's corporate social responsibility activities. Seven of these according to Popoola and Egbulefu (2018) are:

1. Changing social values: the changing value of the society makes it compulsory for organisations not to be static. At the time of Milton Friedman, it was fashionable for organisations not to be concerned about the interests of others stakeholders apart from the shareholders; but not any longer. Matters have changed.
2. Government legislation: though corporate social responsibility activities are humanitarian activities but some legal position that certain percentage of profit must be invested in social scheme makes businesses to be involved in corporate social responsibility. In Nigeria, two per cent of profit before tax is mandatory as education tax that is used in support of education of the Nigerian society.
3. Enlightened self-restrain: the knowledge of the win-win situation makes corporate organisations to be involved in corporate social responsibility as they know that they have many benefits to gain from engagement in corporate social activities.
4. Changing role of manager: the public quotation of some companies makes them more open to the society which necessitates investments in corporate social responsibility activities. Quoted companies on the floor of The Nigerian Stock Exchange are also made to report their corporate social responsibility activities in their annual report of accounts.
5. Personal responsibility: businesses have been made aware that they contribute to the social problems of the society such as the global warming and carbon emission. It is in given palliatives to such problems that organisations also involve in corporate social responsibility.
6. Increased financial resources: organisations in banking, energy, insurance, manufacturing and telecommunication industries declare billions in profit despite Nigerian being a developing nation. In ensuring the wellbeing of the society, organisations engage in corporate social responsibility activities with their financial muscles.
7. Development associations: agitations of different associations and groups in the society also make organisations to engage in corporate social responsibility especially in the provision of infrastructure and security. This is important in Nigeria as the infrastructure provided by government is near-collapse (Oshionebo & Adamolekun, 2011).

Benefits of Corporate Social Responsibility

Gawel (2006) cited in Ijiwo and Terfa (2018) posited that the win-win benefits of corporate social responsibility activities are for the organisation, the society and the environment and the benefits are as follow:

Company/Organisation: improved financial performance, lower operating costs, enhanced brand image and reputation, increased sales and customer loyalty, greater productivity and quality, more ability to attract and retain employees, reduced regulatory oversight, workforce diversity, and product safety and decreased liability.

Society: charitable contributions, employee volunteer programmes, corporate involvement in education, employment welfare programmes, and product safety and quality.

Environment: greater material recyclability, better product durability and functionality, greater use of renewable resources, integration of environmental management tools into business plans including life-cycle assessment and costing as well as environment management standards.

Other benefits of corporate social responsibility to business organisation according to Ajayi (2001) cited in Anaeto and Oni (2018) are staff stability; increased brand value; greater access to finance; recruitment of high quality personnel; motivated people; customers' loyalty; high quality reputation as a result of company's contribution to the welfare of the society; enhanced confidence and trust of stakeholders; growth of investors' confidence in company's shares; enhanced public image; healthier and safer place; harmony between the organisation and the society; and checks conflict between the organisation and members of the society.

Turnover

Turnover involves both costs and benefits to a firm. Survey evidence indicates that most job separations are quits rather than dismissals. The voluntary departure of productive employees is costly, especially when their talent and proprietary knowledge move to a competitor. Many other costs are associated with both voluntary and involuntary turnover. Turnover also has benefits, including the replacement of underperforming employees, providing incentives to perform, and bringing new ideas (Hausknecht and Trevor 2011; Hancock I. 2013). Because the majority of turnover is voluntary, which presumably does not provide net benefits to the firm, the turnover– performance relationship is likely to be mostly negative.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted in this study is ‘The Stakeholder’s Theory’. The stakeholder theory is a theory of organizational management and business ethics that addresses morals and values in managing an organization. The theory says that company leaders should consider Corporate Social Responsibility and the way it affects all persons of interest (Bird, Hall, Momente, & Reggiani, 2007). The stakeholder’s view of strategy integrates both a resource-based view and a market-based view, and adds a socio-political level. One common version of stakeholder theory seeks to define the specific stakeholders of a company and then examine the conditions under which manages treat these parties as stakeholders.

Empirical Review

Scholtens (2008) investigated the relationship between CSR and financial performance of a sample of 289 firms from the US for the period of 1991-2004 by using ordinary least square OLS and Granger Causation techniques of analysis. It was concluded in the study there is significant correlation between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance, though components of CSR like community involvement, employee relations, diversity, environment does not have positive relationship with financial performance in respect of return and risk.

Foote, Gaffney, and Evans, (2010) studied the impact of corporate social responsibility on performance of organization in the perspective of Malcolm Baldrige criteria of the USA and also compared this with the current academic thought. They had gone through various theories of firm’s management, current academic thought and research to carry out the study in the criteria of Malcolm Baldrige. They concluded that there was a positive influence of corporate social responsibility on firm’s performance.

Iqbal, Ahmad, Basheer and Nadeem (2012) examined the connectivity of CSR with financial performance, market value of share and financial leverage of 156 listed companies on Karachi Stock Exchange for the period of 2010-11. They adopted descriptive statistics, correlation and regression to conduct the study. This study showed a mixed result, that CSR negatively affected the market value of those companies and that CSR did not have any influence on those companies and also that there was no relationship between CSR and financial leverage.

Mujahid and Abdullah (2014) studied the dependency of CSR on firm’s financial performance as well as on shareholders’ wealth in Pakistan. They had selected 10 firms which are highly rated as CSR firms and 10 non- CSR firms to see the differences in their financial performances and shareholders wealth as well. They selected the return on equity (ROE) and return on assets (ROA) ratios as financial performance indicators and stock prices and earnings per share (EPS) as representing shareholders’ wealth. They adopted a mixed methodology in the study and concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between CSR and financial performance and shareholders’ wealth.

Ohiokha, Odion and Akhalumeh (2016) analyzed corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance in Nigeria. The study empirically demonstrated the impact of corporate social responsibility on firm’s financial performance. The study adopted pooled survey research design covering twenty-nine (29) firms in Nigeria over a period covering 2005 to 2010. Data collected from the annual reports of the selected firms were analyzed using panel data regression analysis. Result revealed that corporate social responsibility (CSR) had little impact on the financial performance of the sampled companies.

Olaroyeke and Nasieku (2015) conducted an investigation of the effect of corporate social responsibility on the performance of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The population comprised of all the listed manufacturing companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange. Out of the total 74 quoted companies, 15 companies were randomly selected from five different sectors of the manufacturing sector. Descriptive techniques were employed in this

analysis based on primary data collated from responses of senior managers, chief accountants, and chief auditors. Result revealed that corporate social responsibility activities have a moderate positive effect on the performance of manufacturing companies listed on Nigeria Stock Exchange, and that manufacturing companies engage in CSR not only for profitability but for other reasons such as better corporate image, marketing and advertising strategy; employee satisfaction and fulfillment, improve competitive advantages, productivity and business opportunities; organizational values, among others. The study, therefore, recommended that companies engage in CSR policies and strategies not only to improve their performance but also to strengthening its legitimacy, reputation and building competitive advantage

Onyewuchi and Obumeke (2013) studied multinational corporations and the Nigeria economy. The study specifically analyzed how multinational corporations have served as agent of imperialism in any country they operated. In the study it was established that the multinational companies are exploitative as natural resources found in the country which is meant for the development of the country are productively utilized due to de-capitalization of the economy in form of profit repatriation. However, the study emphasized that despite the negative activities of MNCs, they contribute positively in the areas of technological development and creation of employment opportunities

Richard and Okoye (2013) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility on the deposit money banks of Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted in the study with focus review of literatures on the subject matter of corporate social responsibility and financial performance. The study reveals that Social responsibility has a great impact on the society by adding to the infrastructures and development of the society. It was therefore concluded in the study that a company has to give back to the society in which it operates, clean up all forms of pollution it has caused in its course of operation and also provide infrastructural facilities to the society as a way of giving back and developing the society. Hence the study recommended that CSR should be included in the law and enforced on the firms accordingly and that Government should fix a minimum percentage of profit corporate firms.

Ajide and Aderemi (2014) examined the effects of corporate social responsibility activity (CSR) disclosure on bank profitability in Nigeria, using data from annual report and accounts of twelve commercial banks for the year 2012. The study revealed that banks' size and CSR disclosure score have a positive relationship with bank profitability while owners' equity has negative association with bank profitability.

Asuquo, Dada and Onyeogaziri (2018) examined the effect of sustainability reporting on corporate performance of selected quoted brewery firms in Nigeria. To determine the association between sustainability reporting and corporate performance, the study employed data obtained from the audited financial statements of the three brewery firms under study for a period of five years (2012-2016). The result of the study shows that Economic Performance disclosure (ECN), Environmental Performance disclosure (ENV) and Social Performance disclosure (SOC) have no significant effect on return on asset (ROA) of selected quoted firms in Nigeria.

Nnamani, Onyekwelu and Ugwu (2017) empirically studied the effect of sustainability accounting on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Firms used for the study were chosen from the Nigerian brewery sector. Using data sourced from the financial statements of three sampled firms, analysed with ordinary linear regression, the study revealed that sustainability reporting has positive and significant effect on financial performance of firms studied. It depends on corporate social responsibility activities.

Udeh, Abiahu and Tambou (2017) studied the impact of Corporate Governance on Firms' Financial Performance in Nigeria Quoted Banks to determine the banks financial performance before and after the introduction of Code of Corporate Governance in Nigeria by evaluating board composition with a view to determining its impact on firms' financial performance. Using board composition as measure of Corporate Governance and Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) to operationalized financial performance, the study employed data from secondary sources covering the periods of 2003-2014, data was analysed using Ordinary Least Squares Regression Analysis and it was found that board composition has a negative, though non-significant impact on ROCE during the 2003 - 2008 period and during the 2009 – 2014 period.

Summary of the Empirical Review

The review of literatures covered the three objectives. Under the first objective which is the effect of health and safety on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria. Scholtens (2008), Mujahid and Abdullah (2014) were reviewed. Others were the study by, Iqbal, Ahmad, Basheer, & Nadeem, (2012) and so on. Under the second objective, we reviewed the works Onyewuchi and Obumeke (2013).

Review of the third objective included the study by Asuquo, Dada and Onyeogaziri (2018). Having gone through the various works, the researcher found that corporate social responsibilities as posited by many contributors have addressed only the area of financial performances of companies but there was no specific focus on turnover. That is the gap this researcher has found. This study therefore was intended to address the effect of corporate social responsibilities on turnover of Breweries firms in Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design. It is also referred to as casual comparative research that seeks to find out the factors that are associated with certain occurrences, conditions, events or behaviour by analyzing past events or already existing data for possible causal factors (Orjih, 2009).

Area of Study

The area of study is corporate social responsibility of brewery firms in Nigeria. It centered on turnover as the estimated variable while health and safety, education and training, and donations by Nigerian breweries are the estimators.

Sources of Data

The data used for this analysis were taken from secondary sources, namely, the annual financial reports and statements of account of three sampled breweries in Nigeria. These are Nigerian Breweries, Guinness and International Breweries, for the Period 2009 -2020.

Population of Study

The population of breweries in Nigeria is estimated to be nine (9). These are contained in appendix A.

Sample Size Determination

The study adopted the purposive sampling technique and three (3) breweries were selected. The method was used because it is convenient and the three breweries provide relevant data needed for the analysis. The history of these breweries shows that the firms provide reliable and complete secondary data for secondary users.

Method of Data Analysis

The study adopted the simple regression analysis technique. The tools of analysis include simple correlation (r) and coefficient of determination while the test of hypothesis was carried out using the F-test statistic.

Model Specification

The model for this study is specified in implicit form as follows:

$$\text{TURN}_i = f(\text{PUBHS}_i, \text{EDUTRAIN}_i, \text{DONS}_i)$$

Description of Variables in the Models

TURN_i is used to represent turnover of breweries for the period under reference

PUBHS_i represents the cost of public health and safety in the years under consideration

EDUTRAIN_i is the money spent on education and training of staff in the period under study

Results

See Appendix I for data

Data Analysis

Analysis on Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 restated

H₀₁: Public Health and safety do not have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject H₀₁ if p-value < 0.05, otherwise accept

Table 1: Correlation Analysis on Turnover and Public Health and Safety

<i>Model Summary</i>				
<i>Model</i>	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.053 ^a	.003	-.027	109081135.549

a. Predictors: (Constant), PUBH

In table 1, it could be found that there is no strong correlation between turnover and public health and safety because $r = 0.053$. The coefficient of determination $R^2 = 0.003$ or 0.3 percent is considered to be very negligible. It implies that public health and safety did not strongly determine the variations or changes in the turnover of breweries in Nigeria during the period.

Table 2: Test of Significance on Hypothesis 1

<i>ANOVA^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value	
1	Regression	1147364316995685.500	1	1147364316995685.500	.096	.758 ^b
	Residual	404555600511082500.000	34	11898694132678896.00		
	Total	405702964828078210.000	35			

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PUBH

Decision: The test reveals that p-value = 0.758. This value > 0.05, hence we do not reject H₀₁.

Conclusion: We conclude that public health and safety do not have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression of Turnover on Public Health and Safety

<i>Coefficients^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P-value
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	146229331.083	18898262.874		7.738	.000
	PUBH	-.415	1.335	-.053	-.311	.758

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

Table 3 shows the coefficients of the regression model on the relationship between turnover and public health and safety. The model when fitted becomes:

$$TURN_i = 146,229,331.083 - 0.415(PUBH) + \mu$$

This means that public health and safety contributed an estimated constant annual value of N146,229,331.08 to turnover. Likewise, public health and safety was accountable for a marginal decrease of 0.415 over the period. The constant growth is found to be significant but the marginal decrease is negative and non-significant.

Analysis on Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2 restated

H₀₂: Education and Training do not have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject H₀₂ if p-value < 0.05, otherwise accept

Table 4: Correlation Analysis on Turnover and Education & Training

<i>Model Summary</i>				
<i>Model</i>	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.094 ^a	.009	-.020	108751921.748

a. Predictors: (Constant), EDUTRAIN

Table 4 shows that education and training have very weak correlation with turnover at r = 0.094. The coefficient of determination R² = 0.009 supports the outcome since education and training was only able to determine the changes in turnover up to 0.009 only. The change is infinitesimal.

Table 5: Test of Significance on Hypothesis 2

<i>ANOVA^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
1	Regression	3585628378303684.00	1	3585628378303684.00	.303	.585 ^b
	Residual	402117336449774530.00	34	11826980483816898.00		
	Total	405702964828078210.00	35			

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

b. Predictors: (Constant), EDUTRAIN

Decision: Since P-value = 0.585 > 0.05, we do not reject H₀₂.

Conclusion: Therefore, we conclude that education and training did not have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria

Table 6: Regression of Turnover on Education and Training

<i>Coefficients^a</i>						
<i>Model</i>		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P-value
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	147578657.57	18901421.894		7.808	.000
	EDUTRAIN	-.448	.814	-.094	-.551	.585

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

The analysis in table 6 reveals the coefficients for fitting the simple regression model in hypothesis 2.

$$TURN_i = 147,578,657.570 - 0.448(EDUTRAIN_i) + \mu$$

The model estimation shows that education and training made a significant constant contribution to the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria during the period studied. However, the marginal decrease in turnover occasioned by education and training was 0.448 and non-significant.

Analysis on Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3 Restated

H₀₃: Donations do not have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Decision Rule: Reject H₀₃ if p-value < 0.05, otherwise accept.

Table 7: Correlation Analysis on Turnover and Donations

<i>Model Summary</i>				
<i>Mode</i>	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.576 ^a	.332	.312	89310433.343

a. Predictors: (Constant), DONS

The analysis in table 7 shows that there is a high correlation ($r = 0.576$) between turnover and donations by breweries in Nigeria. Donations were able to determine the variations in turnover at 33.2 percent annually, leaving 66.8 percent unexplained. The adjusted $R^2 = 0.312$ is also considerable.

Table 8: Test of Significance on Hypothesis 3

		<i>ANOVA^a</i>				
	<i>Model</i>	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value
1	Regression	134506945697757312.00	1	134506945697757312.00	16.863	.000 ^b
	Residual	271196019130320896.00	34	7976353503832968.00		
	Total	405702964828078210.00	35			

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

b. Predictors: (Constant), DONS

Decisions: Since the outcome of the test is $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$, we do not accept H_{03} .

Conclusion: We therefore conclude that donations have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Table 9: Regression of Turnover on Donations

		<i>Coefficients^a</i>				
	<i>Model</i>	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P-value
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	113172989.281	16740217.145		6.761	.000
	DONS	.545	.133	.576	4.106	.000

a. Dependent Variable: TUR

The regression coefficients in table 4.10 show that both the constant and variable contributions of donations to the changes in turnover were both significant because the p-values are less than 0.05. The model for this estimation is:

$$TURN_i = 113,172,989.281 - 0.545(DONS_i) + \mu$$

The model shows that constant annual donations estimated at about ₦113.172 million contributed to the variations in turnover. On the other hand, there was a marginal variation of 0.545 in turnover occasioned by donations during the period. Both the constant and marginal variations are significant.

Summary of Findings

- 1) Public health and safety do not have significant effect on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.
- 2) Education and training do not have significant effect on turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.
- 3) Donations have significant effect on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Many studies have been carried out in corporate social responsibility of the oil and gas as well as in the manufacturing firms in the past. However, the effort of the researcher was to focus on the effect of CSR on the turnover of brewery firms in Nigeria. The study was able to reveal that donations and gifts component of corporate social responsibility is significant and needs to be continuously pursued to make the environment stable for both the communities and the companies involved. However, public health and education and training were not significant. So, the average judgment of this outcome is that corporate social responsibility has not really made much impact in the area of brewery firms in Nigeria.

Recommendation

- 1) Breweries in Nigeria should buckle up in public and safety efforts in the areas where they operate. A healthy workforce and the immediate environment and communities should benefit from the corporate social responsibilities of the breweries and improve the quality of life in those areas.
- 2) The management of breweries in Nigeria should up the game by putting more into education and training of persons in the environment where they operate and especially the improvement of skills and development of manpower of own staff. Currently, they have not done that very well hence this has negatively affected the turnover of the sector.
- 3) The Management of breweries in Nigeria should as a matter of responsibility continue to give donations and gifts to charities and orphanages, sports entertainments, infrastructural development and such like. This will reduce industrial unrests, agitations and protests in the areas where the firms are located.

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**APPENDIX I
 NIGERIAN BREWERIES PLC**

YEAR	TURNOVER #’000	PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY #’000	EDUCATION AND TRAINING #’000	DONATIONS TO NGOS AND ASSOCIATION #’000
2009	164,206,848	343,867	1,036,602	100,517,175
2010	185,862,785	293,864	958,661	67,123,955
2011	207,303,379	413,855	97,449,302	40,400
2012	252,674,213	633,468	1,944,958	81,674,450
2013	268,613,518	645,676	2,109,478	207,193,655
2014	266,372,475	659,316	1,884,807	140,203,543
2015	293,905,792	849,388	2,219,500	131,064,450
2016	313,743,147	933,694	1,978,372	145,972,218
2017	344,562,517	894,892	2,233,463	76,885,994
2018	324,388,500	883,075	1,573,073	57,700,667
2019	323,007,470	842,628	1,430,626	94,767,679
2020	337,046,213	984,420	1,032,301	634,547,452

Source: Annual reports and Accounts of Nigerian Breweries Plc

GUINNESS NIGERIA PLC

YEAR	TURNOVER #’000	PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY #’000	EDUCATION AND TRAINING #’000	DONATIONS TO NGOS AND ASSOCIATIONS #’000
2009	89,146,207	606,000	186,461	26,200
2010	109,366,975	77,926,144	16,553	87,084,528
2011	123,663,125	3,813,188	810,000	46,133,852
2012	126,288,184	20,943,735	775,000	118,189,873
2013	122,463,538	26,095,075	32,470	13,919
2014	109,202,120	3,370	1,520	6,516
2015	118,495,882	3,075	1,250	6,882
2016	101,973,030	17,979	16,195	33,811
2017	125,919,817	5,000	1,775	5,000
2018	142,975,792	5,000	1,775	5,000
2019	131,498,393	4,598	1,633	4,567
2020	104,376,015	3,649	1,296	3,625

Source: Annual Statements of Account of Guinness Nigeria Plc

INTERNATIONAL BREWERIES PLC

YEAR	TURNOVER #’000	PUBLIC HEALTH AND SAFETY #’000	EDUCATION AND TRAINING #’000	DONATIONS TO NGOS AND ASSOCIATION #’000
2009	931,921	80,435	18,939,808	2,752,850
2010	1,616,503	139,521	32,853	4,775,094
2011-	4,794,946	413,855	97,449,302	40,400
2012	9,908,167	633,468	1,944,958	81,674,450
2013	17,388,632	3,029	119,930	77,000
2014	18,493,907	4,374	86,912	42,300
2015	20,649,295	12,300	91,363	30,354
2016	23,269,369	4,007	5,508	79,592
2017	32,711,218	1,300	75,266	53,248
2018	120,610,825	4,000	215,374	130,700
2019	132,351,500	30,149	210,233	62,010
2020	136,790,573	12,681	83,808	310,420

Source: Annual Statement of International Breweries Plc